

YOUTHS UNEMPLOYMENT: THE WAY OUT

By

ADEAGBO, MATTHEW OLUWASEUN

School of Arts and Social Sciences Department of Economics

Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo

Abstract

Nigerian youth are faced with a lot of challenges in this 21st century the solution of which can help to propel the wheel of development of the nation. This paper examined Nigerian youth unemployment palaver vis-a-vis job creation. The study employed the use of a self developed questionnaire which had been validated by experts to collect required information from randomly selected respondents. The information so collected was analyzed using chi-square statistical method. From the findings, it was revealed that unemployment abound in Nigeria environment. The result also reveals that young graduates in Nigeria prefer white collar jobs than being self employed. In addition it was discovered that a high percentage of those involved in social disturbance are the unemployed youth. The findings conclusively confirm that job creation/entrepreneurship activities among youths will reduce the menace of unemployment among Nigerians. Based on the above, various recommendations were made among which are the introduction of entrepreneurship training in school curricular, craft courses as compulsory elective in tertiary institutions., graduate farmers scheme, enlightenment programmes on self employment schemes, and adequate infrastructural provision by government to encourage investors, among others.

Keywords: *Youths, Unemployment and Wayout.*

Introduction

Obviously the issue of unemployment is not new in the Nigeria economy and other nations but its effect especially on young graduates/youth nowadays is highly pronounced and this has now made it a

Vital issue for be economists and the nation at large. A country is normally said to be operating under full employment when it is operating on the production possibility frontier. In that case, all those workers who are willing, able, capable and available for work are fully engaged. However, when an economy is operating under the production possibility frontier, this means that a certain percentage of the labour force that is willing, able, capable and available for work is unemployed;

Nigeria has long left behind (in the 1960s and 1970s) the possibility of full employment when everyone that is willing, able and capable to work gets something to do, even with jobs awaiting high school graduates who so wish. The challenges of unemployment in Nigeria became a serious issue especially from the mid-1980s, when the structural adjustment programme was foisted on the nation by the military regime. The introduction of the structural adjustment programme was sequel upon the failure of Shagari's government's economic stabilization act of 1982 popularly known as Austerity Measure which aimed at ameliorating the pains of the drastic fall in foreign exchange earnings and control.

The structural adjustment programme was a step aimed at getting out of the country's problem by seeking IMF, loan which came with thirteen conditionalities one of which was a cut in public expenditure (that is, massive retrenchments) which exacerbated the unemployment situation. Unemployment has been seen as one of the major cankerworm plaguing the country today with its resultant havoc of armed robbery, bribery and corruption, drug trafficking, bombing here and there and so on. Many unemployed graduates today are suspected to be the brain behind all the above vices. This corroborates the saying that an idle hand is the devils workshop. The unemployed youth seek jobs after graduation but which are not forth coming. The above effect is seen in all sectors of the economy causing, depression for parents who send their wards to school all to come

out without being employed and still rely on these parents for survival. The unemployment saga also causes depression for students themselves. These students see themselves as unlucky having toiled day and night to come out in flying colours but with no hope of gainful employment. Many government agencies and institutions both at the local, state or federal levels claim no vacancy to absorb the teeming population of the young graduates, so also the few private agencies hence the need for job creation through entrepreneurship training.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is examining among other things the following:

- i. Whether unemployment abounds in Nigeria environment or not
- ii. If unemployment abounds and if so, what are the causes?
- iii. The effect of unemployment on the Nigerian society.
- iv. How job creation and entrepreneurship among Nigerian youth can be encouraged to combat the challenges of unemployment.

Conceptual Framework

It is very difficult to accurately define the concept youth. The youth are younger generations; each environment determines who is a youth and what a youth does. The United Nations (2005) defined the youth as the age group between 15 and 24 years. In Nigeria, this age range falls within those that are in secondary schools or about to finish and those in tertiary institutions or have finished depending on their course of study and institutions attended but they are some non literate youth. In view of this, Webster (1994) described youth as a state of being young, the period from childhood to maturity, an early stage of development. Also Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English (2005) defined youth as the period of being young,

especially the period between a child and being fully grown, early life. This definition is further corroborated by Ndu (2000) and Yusuf (2001) by who agree that youths are neither adolescent nor children but individuals making transition between childhood and adulthood that are generally in their productive years and are found in all spheres of life.

Some scholars are of the view that youths can be defined using the chronological age, the legal perspective, cultural perspective and class base model. The chronological age definition sees an individual as a youth, when he / she consider him/her self younger than other adults. For example the governor of Osun State, Ogbeni Rauf Aregbesola said he is a youth, the Nigerian president Dr. Goodluck Ebele Jonathan in one of his speech says that these are the regime of youths, this is in Compares to some people they themselves view as adult. This definition sees an adult as someone not very active, someone who has reach the age of 65years and above.

Youth from the legal perspective are those that have reached certain age considered by law to be responsible for any action taken whether good or bad, those that can bear the consequence of their actions themselves. In Nigeria the Federal Road Safety Commission (FRSC) says before someone can be issued a driving license he must at least have reached 18 years of age, also before one can vote in Nigeria he must have attained the age of 18 years. The University of Ibadan believes youth who can be admitted into university must have reached the age of 18years but Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife is of diverse opinion to this.

Youth from the cultural perspective is somebody who is not yet tied down by a fixed responsibility. "Odo" (Youth) in Yoruba culture are those who are yet to be tied down by family responsibility, an unmarried individual. The class base model definition of youth sees a youth as somebody between his third-seventh birthday (i.e 21years) and fifth-seventh birthday (i.e 35years); hence to them a youth is somebody between the age range of 21-35years.

A little deviation from the above, the Nigeria's National Youth Development Policy as pointed out by Onwuasoanya (2007) state that the youth comprises all young persons of age 18 to 30 who are also within the school age of senior secondary school and the higher institution. Despite all these differences in definition, there exists an area of similarity, these centres on the idea of age. However, for the purpose of this write up, youth will be divided into two major groups, viz:

- > Youth in senior secondary schools, Polytechnics, Monotechnics, Universities and other tertiary institutions
- > Youths who are already in the open society either as part of the labour force or as dependent on the working population.

The thrust of this paper is to investigate if unemployment abounds among youths and the possible way out of such a menace.

According to Anyaele (2003), unemployment is a situation in which people who are willing, able and capable to work cannot find paid job. Salako, Adeagbo and Ajiteru (2012) defined unemployment as a situation where people who fall within the age of working population, capable and willing to work are unable to obtain any befitting job.

Summarily therefore, unemployment can be said to be a situation in which people who are willing, able and capable to work and legally qualified cannot find paid job.

According to Salako, Adeagbo and Ajiteru (2012) various types of unemployment abound, these include:

- Underemployment: A situation where the potentiality of a worker is not fully utilized
- Frictional Unemployment: Lapses between leaving a job and getting another one.
- Deficient Demand (cyclical) Unemployment: Decrease in quantity of

- goods demanded in a country leading to retrenchment of workers
- Structural unemployment:** This is deliberate when someone refuses to take up any paid employment
- Seasonal Unemployment:** This is caused by seasonal change that affects some types of work
- **Search Unemployment:** This arises when some people turn down offers to work, in search of better paid one
 - **Technological Unemployment:** This is caused as a result of change in production technique
- Salako, Adeagbo & Ajiteru (2012) also identified the following as causes of unemployment in Nigeria.
- **Absence of industrialization to absorb the teeming population of young school leavers**
 - **Poor agricultural system which makes agriculture unattractive to young school leavers**
 - **Lack of social amenities in the rural areas which makes the youth prefer settling down in the urban areas even when they can get employment in rural areas.**
 - **Excess of supply over demand which causes retrenchment of workers**
 - **Economic recession which forces many industries to fold up**
 - **Faulty educational system which makes people to be job seekers rather than job creators**
 - **Population increase with no avenue for employment**
 - **High cost of education leading to student drop out of school, or not progressing beyond secondary education**
 - **Faulty development plan (establishing more schools without job opportunity)**
 - **Geographical immobility of labour**
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Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated for testing in the study

- HO₁:** Unemployment does not abound in Nigeria environment
- HO₂:** Young graduates prefer to be self employed than looking for white collar job
- HO₃:** A high percentage of those involved in social disturbance are the unemployed youths
- HO₄:** Job creation/entrepreneurship activities among youths have little or no effect on unemployment among Nigerians.

Empirical Methodology Sampling

The population for this study comprised randomly selected Corpers from AFIJIO local government NYSC secretariat, staff of Emmanuel Alayande College of Education Model High School, Oyo and staff of the Polytechnic Ibadan. Thirty (30) (10 each from the selected groups) respondents were randomly sampled.

Instrumentation:

A self developed questionnaire was used to collect data for this study. It consisted of three sections (sections A, B and C) Section A contained the background information on the respondents concerning gender, age, qualifications, etc.

Section B of the questionnaire was made up of 10 items which deal with various aspect of youth's life vis-a-vis unemployment and job creation, section C of the questionnaire contained an open ended statement requesting the respondents to suggest ways by which unemployment can be reduced and job creation encouraged among Nigerian youths.

Analysis of Data

The paper employs simple percentage method in analyzing the data collected while all the hypotheses were tested the chi-square statistical method.

Table 1

Unemployment does not abound in Nigeria environment

Opinion	Fo	Fe	Fo-Fe	(Fo-Fe) ²	(Fo-Fe) ² fe
Agree	-	15	-15	225	15
Disagree	30	15	15	225	15
Total	30				30

The computed $x^2 = 30$

Decision Rule: At 5% significant level, the null hypotheses should be rejected if x^2 computed is greater than x^2 value from the table otherwise accept.

X^2 (1) degree of freedom of 5% = 3.841 since x^2 cal $>$ X^2 tab (i.e 30 $>$ 3.841) then the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This implies that unemployment abound in Nigeria environment.

Table 2:

Young graduates prefer to be self employed than looking for white collar job

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Opinion	Fo	Fe	Fo-Fe	(Fo-Fe) ²	(Fo-Fe) ² fe
Agree	21	15	6	36	2.4
Disagree	9	15	-6	36	2.4
Total	30				4.8

Decision Rule: At 5% significant level, the null hypothesis should be rejected if χ^2 computed is greater than χ^2 tabulated otherwise accept.

From the result of findings $\chi^2_{cal} > \chi^2_{tab}$ (i.e $4.8 > 3.841$) it is revealed that young graduates prefer white collar jobs than being self employed. The null hypothesis is rejected while we accept the alternative hypothesis

Table 3

A high percentage of those involved in social disturbance are unemployed youths

Opinion	Fo	Fe	Fo-Fe	(Fo-Fe) ²	(Fo-Fe) ² fe
Agree	20	15	5	25	1.7
Disagree	10	15	-5	25	1.7
Total	30				3.4

Decision Rule: At 5% significant level the null hypothesis should be rejected if χ^2 computed is greater than χ^2 tabulated. From the finding since $\chi^2_{cal} < \chi^2_{tab}$ (i.e $3.4 < 3.841$) we therefore accept the null hypothesis that, a high percentage of those involved in social disturbance are unemployed youth and

thus reject the alternative hypothesis

Table 4

Job Creation/ Entrepreneurship activities among youth have little or no effect on unemployment among them.

Opinion	Fo	Fe	Fo-Fe	(Fo-Fe) ²	(Fo-Fe) ² / fe
Agree	6	15	-9	81	5.4
Disagree	24	15	9	81	5.4
Total	30				10.8

Decision Rule: At 5% significance level the null hypothesis should be rejected if χ^2 computed is greater than χ^2 tabulated.

From the result of the findings since $\chi^2_{cal} > \chi^2_{tab}$ (i.e 10.8 > 3.841) the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and the alternative accepted. This implies that job creation / entrepreneurship activity among youths will reduce the menace of unemployment among Nigerians

Discussion of Findings

The findings in this study have revealed that unemployment rate is very high among Nigerians especially young graduates, though the fact that many of them prefer white collar job was acceded to. This conforms to Paquettes's (2009) submission which made him to advise youths to establish small scale businesses. Unemployment was traced to the fact that many Nigeria graduates are trained to be job seekers and that job creation has been seen as the high responsibility of the government.

In addition it is erroneously believed that job creation requires huge initial capital which many potential entrepreneurs may not be able to afford. The findings also revealed that various social disturbances experienced in the society are perpetrated by the unemployed youths.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings the following are recommended:

- * Entrepreneurship training should be included in the school curriculum both at the senior secondary school level and at tertiary institution
- * Craft courses should be introduced as vocational compulsory elective courses in the tertiary institutions (as the case is at Tai Solarin University of Education) and be given serious attention.
- * Graduate farmers' scheme should be introduced by giving graduates of Agricultural Science hectares of land and loans with little interest rate and using only their certificate as collateral to practice what they have learnt.
- * Government should provide adequate infrastructural facilities such as good road network, regular supply of electricity etc which will encourage private investors.
- * Enlightenment programmes on self employment should be given the widest publicity
- * Soft loans with no collateral security should be provided for entrepreneurs to boost the establishment and development of their businesses.

Conclusion

Youths who are the future of the nation, need to be meaningfully employed. A nation with high percentage of its youth in the unemployment market is wasting abundant human resources hence both the government

and financial institutions have a role to play in ensuring that the abundant labour supply (majorly youth) are not wasted. The procedure and methodology of giving facilities by financial institutions and government need to be monitored. In this regard, government needs to institute monitoring committees to see to the appropriateness of the dissemination to the target audience such that the genuine beneficiaries are not fenced out.

Youths should at this time look inward on what to do. No government job, no private job. Then what next? Youths should create job for themselves. How? Through establishment of small scale enterprises. E.g. Handsets / accessories, petty trading, casual works and so on.

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